

Impact of Ergonomics at Information Technology Sector During Hybrid Model of Work Scenario in The Present and Future Trends

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Abstract

Ergonomics, often referred to as the science of fitting the job to the individual, plays a pivotal role in enhancing productivity, health and overall well-being of employees in various Industries. The emphasis on Ergonomics is even more pronounced in the field of Information Technology (IT), where Professionals typically spend prolonged hours in sedentary positions, interacting with technology interfaces. Given this backdrop, understanding the Ergonomics behavior becomes a matter of paramount importance, especially when aiming for sustainable human resource development.

Keywords: Ergonomics, fatigue, multidisciplinary, significance, integration.

INTRODUCTION

Coimbatore District, renowned for its vibrant IT hub, houses a significant number of IT firms ranging from start-ups to multinational corporations. With thousands of IT professionals working in the district, the human resource implications of Ergonomics become essential to explore. Professionals in this domain face unique challenges such as, long hours of computer usage, inadequate workstation design and the pressure of meeting deadlines, which often lead to health issues such as musculoskeletal disorders, eye strain and mental fatigue. These health challenges can further affect absenteeism, job satisfaction, and productivity and employee turnover rates, making it a crucial human resource concern.

This study, therefore, aims to shed light on the intricate relationship between Ergonomics behavior and key human resource factors among IT Professionals in Coimbatore District. By delving deep into this relationship, the research seeks to

provide insights for employers, policymakers and professionals, assisting them in creating a work environment that promotes both health and productivity. In an era where technology dominates the workspace, understanding and addressing Ergonomics can significantly contribute to enhancing the quality of professional life, leading to more robust, sustainable and a thriving IT Industry in the region.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The Information Technology (IT) Industry has grown exponentially over the past few decades which becomes an integral part of modern life and economy. Within this rapidly growing and competitive field, the well-being, productivity and satisfaction of IT Professionals are of paramount importance. Despite its importance, a comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to an optimal work environment, particularly from an Ergonomic perspective, remains a complex and multifaceted issue. Ergonomics is not a

monolithic concept but encompasses a variety of mechanistic, biological and psychosocial factors. Understanding how these factors interact and contribute to the overall Ergonomic environment will provide a more nuanced view. This includes evaluating physical layouts, equipment design, work schedules, social interactions, psychological demands and more as an effective research study.

Since Ergonomics is frequently delegated to the realm of safety Professionals, it paves the way for the Human Resource Industry to complement less absenteeism, increased productivity, happier employee, efficient performance, optimum potential, mental stability, physical fitness and healthier employees. The advantages that Ergonomics gives the employees has a great focus on the growth of the organization as a whole which leads to the development of the society and economic growth of the country as well. There prevails a wide range of issues and problems, which comprise Ergonomic features that are due to the interdisciplinary nature of science and behavioral aspects. The Ergonomic technique is drawn from the achievements of the biological sciences, technical knowhow and organizational strategies. Ergonomics also reveals that, there is a determined change in the behavior of employees due to mechanistic, biological and psychological or psychosocial aspects.

Based on the above-mentioned aspects the following are considered as problem for the study,

Do employees working in Information Technology Industries agree towards modular-structured work systems based on mechanistic, biological and psychosocial factors?

What do employees perceive about existing Ergonomics practices with Information Technology Industry?

What is the opinion of employees on Ergonomic factors at workstation and what are their suggestions towards Ergonomic factors?

What is the significance of mechanistic, biological and psychosocial factors of Ergonomics on Ergonomic factors at workstation?

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

To analyze the demographic and sociographic variables of the employees working in the Information Technology Industry.

To ascertain the implication of mechanistic, biological and psychosocial factors of Ergonomics towards Ergonomic factors at workstations.

To analyze the modular-structured work systems of the Information Technology employees based on mechanistic, biological and psychosocial factors.

To estimate the perception of employees towards existing Ergonomics practices with Information Technology Industries.

To evaluate the employee's opinion on Ergonomic factors at workstation.

To evaluate and appraise the suggestions of employees towards Ergonomic factors.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The optimum scope of Human Resource Management process is closely linked to the nature of Ergonomics, the science dealing with the adaptation of work by the human body in terms of its features and characteristics of mental and physical aspects and the need to create and ensure optimal working conditions to improve not only performance but also comfort and efficiency. However, Ergonomics is the science with more creative determined solutions that takes into account, not only the security issues and the responsibility

for compliance, but also the humanization issues, including improved comfort, satisfaction and employee fulfillment. The main scope of the study is that Ergonomics will help the Information Technology Industry to know about the perception of employees about factors related to Ergonomics which will conceptually help them in the decision-making process. Thus, the Conceptual Model Framework is designed to show the significance of Mechanistic, Biological and Psychosocial factors of Ergonomics towards employee benefits at the workstation.

ABOUT ERGONOMICS

Ergonomics, derived from the Greek words "ergon" (work) and "nomos" (laws), fundamentally seeks to understand the interaction between humans and other elements of a system. This multidisciplinary field bridges knowledge from anatomy, physiology, psychology, engineering and statistics to design and evaluate tasks, jobs, products, environments and systems to make them compatible with the abilities, the needs and the limitations of people (Dul et al., 2012).

Historically, the birth of Ergonomics can be traced back to the industrial revolution, but it was during World War II that the discipline truly came to the forefront. The complex nature of military systems necessitated a better understanding of the human operator, marking a pronounced shift from intuition-based design to systematic study (Meister, 1999).

THERE ARE TYPICALLY THREE PRIMARY DOMAINS IN ERGONOMICS

PHYSICAL ERGONOMICS

Physical Ergonomics deals with the human body's responses to physical and physiological loads. Factors such as body posture, material handling, workspace design, repetitive movements and

workplace layout fall under this domain (Kroemer & Grandjean, 1997)

COGNITIVE ERGONOMICS

Cognitive Ergonomics concerns mental processes like perception, memory, reasoning and motor responses, especially as they interact with complex systems. Topics such as mental workload, decision-making, skilled performance, human-computer interaction, human reliability and training are some of its key areas (Wickens & Hollands, 2000).

ORGANIZATIONAL ERGONOMICS

Organizational Ergonomics dives into the optimization of sociotechnical systems, encompassing topics like communication, workforce scheduling, teamwork, participative design and cooperative work (Hendrick & Kleiner, 2002).

The significance of Ergonomics has grown remarkably with the evolution of modern work environments. With the rise of technology and the digital era, there's an increasing awareness of the importance of user-friendly designs and systems that take into account the human factor. Adverse Ergonomic conditions, on the other hand, have been linked to a range of musculoskeletal disorders, which are significant contributors to work-related illnesses and absenteeism (Punnett & Wegman, 2004).

Organizations worldwide have realized the benefits of Ergonomic interventions not only in terms of employee's health and well-being but also in productivity, efficiency and Quality of Work. Consequently, the field has expanded beyond its traditional boundaries, encompassing areas like inclusive design and user experience.

ERGONOMICS IN THE IT INDUSTRY

The Information Technology (IT) Industry, characterized by intensive

computer usage, rapid technological advancements and evolving work cultures, presents unique Ergonomic challenges. From the design of computer hardware and software interfaces to the layout of modern tech workplaces, Ergonomics plays an instrumental role in ensuring that tech Professionals maintain health, well-being and optimal productivity.

1. THE EVOLVING IT WORK ENVIRONMENT

a. Historical Perspective: The evolution of workstations from large mainframe setups to personal desktops and now to mobile and remote solutions (Cakir, Hart, & Stewart, 1980).

b. The Remote Work Trend: Impact of Ergonomics in home offices, the challenges and solutions (Haynes, 2011).

2. PHYSICAL ERGONOMICS IN IT

a. Computer Workstations: Design, layout and health implications of prolonged usage (Kumar, 1994).

b. Input Devices: The Ergonomics of keyboards, mice, touch screens and emerging technologies (Bergqvist et al., 1995).

c. Seating and Posture: Importance of Ergonomic chairs and the role of posture in preventing musculoskeletal disorders (Mandal, 1981).

3. COGNITIVE ERGONOMICS IN IT

a. Software and User Interface Design: Principles for designing user-friendly and intuitive interfaces (Shneiderman & Plaisant, 2010).

b. Information Overload: Cognitive strain in the digital age and strategies to mitigate its effects (Eppler & Mengis, 2004).

4. ORGANIZATIONAL ERGONOMICS IN IT

a. Work Schedule: The effects of prolonged work hours, shifts and the 24/7

work culture (Caruso et al., 2004).

b. Team Dynamics: Collaborative tools, virtual teams and their Ergonomic implications (Olson & Olson, 2000).

5. HEALTH IMPLICATIONS

a. Musculoskeletal Disorders: Prevalence, causes and preventive measures in the IT Industry (Harrington & Szigeti, 2002).

b. Vision Issues: Computer Vision Syndrome and its prevention (Blehm et al., 2005).

6. FUTURE OF ERGONOMICS IN IT

a. Emerging Technologies: Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality and Ergonomic considerations (LaViola Jr, 2000).

b. Sustainability: Ergonomic solutions that align with environmental and social sustainability (Dul & Neumann, 2009).

ABOUT CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on the conceptual framework the factors job specialization, skill requirement related to mechanistic aspect, workspace design, work environment, work time schedule related to biological aspect, job autonomy, job feedback, task variety/clarity, mental overload/underload, training and promotion, organizational commitment related to psychosocial aspect are considered to be independent variables. The dimensions body postures, desk related, chair related, monitor, keyboard / mouse and work habits related to Ergonomic factors of workstation are considered to be dependent variables.

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

MECHANISTIC ASPECT IN THE CONTEXT OF IT WORKSPACES

The mechanistic aspects, especially in the realm of IT, aren't merely

about task division or skill proficiency. They're about creating a symbiotic relationship between the professional and their environment. This integration ensures that as Professionals delve deeper into their specialized roles and hone their high-demand skills, their workspaces dynamically adapt, ensuring comfort, efficiency and holistic well-being.

1. JOB SPECIALIZATION

Job specialization, in essence, delineates the partitioning of tasks within an organization, where each individual focuses on a specific function or subset of tasks. This intricate segmentation, particularly in fast-evolving sectors like IT, holds notable Ergonomic and organizational implications.

EVOLUTION OF SPECIALIZED ROLES

With the rapid evolution of technology, new niches are consistently emerging. For example, a few decades ago, an IT Professional might have been responsible for a broad range of tasks. Today, we have roles as specific as cloud solution architects, cybersecurity specialists or machine learning engineers. This granularity inherently demands unique toolsets and environments tailored to the tasks at hand.

WORKSPACE IMPLICATIONS

Specialized roles often entail unique software and hardware configurations. For instance, a graphics designer might require a high-resolution, colour-accurate monitor with a drawing tablet, while a database administrator might need multiple screens to monitor real-time data and system health. As tasks get more specialized, the workspaces need to adapt to accommodate these specific needs.

COLLABORATION AND COMMUNICATION

Specialized roles can sometimes lead to silos within organizations. The workspace, both virtual and physical, needs to facilitate communication between these specialized entities. Meeting rooms equipped with the latest conferencing tools, collaborative software platforms and open floor plans that encourage spontaneous interactions become essential for organization's growth.

2. SKILL REQUIREMENT

The skill requirement of a role, especially in the IT sector, doesn't just determine the qualifications or certifications an individual possess, but it translates into the depth of knowledge, proficiency in tools and adaptability to the swiftly changing tech landscapes.

HIGH-TECH ERGONOMIC SETUPS

High-skill jobs, particularly in IT, often involve prolonged interaction with technology. Multiple monitors might be necessary for coding, data analysis or system monitoring. It's not just about quantity but the quality of these setups, such as high-refresh-rate screens for software developers or color - calibrated screens for UI/UX designers becomes paramount.

ADAPTIVE WORKSPACES

High-skill IT Professionals often juggle multiple tasks. An adaptive workspace that allows easy transition between tasks—like adjustable monitor arms, docking stations for laptops or even standing desks for alternating work postures - becomes a necessity in work stations.

LEARNING AND UPGRADATION

High-skill roles in IT are synonymous with continuous learning. With the frenetic pace of technological advancements, Professionals must

regularly upgrade their skills. Workspaces should cater to this by incorporating environments conducive to learning - be it through quiet zones for focused online courses, whiteboards for brainstorming or tech-equipped rooms for virtual workshops.

SAFETY AND HEALTH

Prolonged engagement with advanced tech setups can sometimes lead to health issues like, repetitive strain injuries or digital eye strain. Specialized Ergonomic equipment - like keyboards with negative tilt, vertical mice or monitor screen filters - can help mitigate these risks.

BIOLOGICAL ASPECT IN THE Context of Information Technology Workspaces

The biological aspects, especially in the domain of IT, emphasize the integration of human physiological needs with the demands of the job. A keen understanding and execution of these factors ensure that as technology and tasks evolve, the health and well-being of the Professionals remain at the forefront. This synthesis ensures not only a productive workforce but also a satisfied and healthy work space.

WORKSPACE DESIGN

The design of a workspace can profoundly impact the physiological well-being of its occupants. This, not only creates the physical layout, but it's more about creating an environment that's both functional and conducive to health.

Furniture Design

Ergonomically designed furniture supports natural body postures, reducing the risk of musculoskeletal disorders. For instance, adjustable chairs can support the lumbar region, while height-adjustable desks can promote both sitting and standing work positions.

Color Psychology

The colors used in a workspace can evoke different physiological and emotional

responses. For instance, blues and greens are known to have a calming effect and can enhance concentration, while warmer colors like reds and yellows can inspire energy and creativity.

Lighting

Natural light has been associated with increased productivity and better mood. Workspaces that allow ample daylight, possibly through large windows or skylights, can help in regulating the body's internal clock. Additionally, the use of adjustable artificial lighting that mimics natural light patterns can help in reducing eye strain, especially for IT Professionals who spend considerable time in front of screens.

Ambiance

Incorporating elements like indoor plants can improve air quality and increased feelings of well-being. Likewise, open spaces, artwork and quiet zones can offer a respite from the intense focus required in IT roles.

WORK ENVIRONMENT

The broader work environment, especially in IT, has a direct bearing on the biological health of Professionals.

Quality of Lighting

Poor lighting can lead to visual discomfort, eye strain and even headaches. In the context of IT, where screen usage is pervasive, ensuring adequate and diffused lighting is paramount. Anti-glare screens can also be employed to minimize reflections and reduce visual stress.

Ambient Noise Levels

A balanced noise level is crucial. While complete silence might be unrealistic and even stifling, excessive noise can be disruptive. Soundproofing, white noise machines or noise-cancelling headphones can be invaluable for IT Professionals who need focused concentration.

Temperature and Climate Control

The ideal temperature for workspaces is often considered to be between 22-25°C (72-77°F). Consistent temperatures can prevent discomfort and advanced HVAC systems can ensure clean air circulation, which is crucial in maintaining cognitive functions and reducing fatigue.

Air Quality

Especially in closed office spaces, air quality can deteriorate, leading to the "sick building syndrome". Installing air purifiers, maintaining HVAC systems and incorporating greenery can help in ensuring that employees breathe cleaner air.

WORK TIME SCHEDULE

The human body operates on a natural cycle known as the circadian rhythm, influencing sleep patterns, hormone release and even digestion. Aligning work schedules with this rhythm can have pronounced benefits.

Circadian Alignment

IT Professionals, especially those involved in global projects, often work odd hours. However, as much as possible, aligning work timings to daylight hours can boost alertness and productivity.

Breaks and Rest Periods

Short, regular breaks can prevent cognitive saturation and physical discomfort. Software like the "Pomodoro Technique" or even wearable tech reminders can prompt employees to take short breaks, stretch or rest their eyes.

Flexible Hours and Shifts

Given the diverse roles in IT, some jobs might not adhere to the traditional 9-5 schedule. Offering flexibility - like compressed work weeks, staggered shifts or remote working options can allow employees to work at their most productive hours.

PSYCHOSOCIAL ASPECT IN THE CONTEXT OF IT WORKSPACES

1. JOB AUTONOMY

Job autonomy refers to the level of independence and discretion that the employees possess in their tasks and decision-making process.

Benefits of Autonomy

A significant amount of research has illustrated that employees with higher job autonomy often exhibit increased job satisfaction, enhanced motivation and greater overall well-being. They tend to be more innovative and show better problem-solving abilities (Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M., 2000).

Workspace Implications

Autonomy often allows employees to customize their workspaces, ensuring they're conducive to their individual work patterns. This could involve choices in seating arrangements, the positioning of tech tools or even ambient factors like lighting.

Balancing Autonomy

While autonomy is beneficial, it needs to be paired with accountability. Open communication channels and regular check-ins ensure that while employees have the freedom to execute tasks, they align with broader organizational goals.

2. JOB FEEDBACK

Feedback mechanisms play a vital role in Professional development and task direction.

Benefits of Continuous Feedback

Regular feedback helps employees understand their performance metrics, align with organizational goals and continuously refine their skills (London, M., 2003).

Workspace Implications

Feedback can lead to changes in workspace dynamics. For instance, a

developer receiving feedback on collaboration might opt for a workstation closer to team members. Similarly, feedback on posture or workstation use can result in Ergonomic adjustments.

3. TASK VARIETY/CLARITY

Task variety and clarity can influence both motivation and the structural setup of workstations.

Task Clarity

Clearly defined roles and responsibilities minimize confusion, leading to a streamlined and organized workspace. When IT Professionals understand their primary tasks, they can set up their stations efficiently, with tools and equipment that support those specific tasks.

Task Variety

Varied roles might necessitate versatile workspaces. An IT Professional handling coding, testing and client presentations might need a desk setup that's adaptable for each task.

4. MENTAL OVERLOAD/UNDERLOAD

Balancing cognitive demand is crucial for maintaining engagement and preventing burnout.

Cognitive Overload

Overwhelm can arise from excessive multitasking, constant interruptions or a barrage of tasks. Workspace solutions might involve noise-cancelling headphones, privacy screens or even simple organizational tools to manage tasks effectively.

Cognitive Underload

The opposite, under-stimulation or a lack of challenging tasks, can lead to disengagement. Dynamic workspaces that allow for quick shifts between tasks, communal areas for collaboration or even recreational zones for breaks can mitigate this scenario.

5. TRAINING AND PROMOTION

Learning Environments

Dedicated spaces equipped with the latest tech tools can facilitate training sessions. Additionally, open spaces for collaborative workshops or quiet zones for focused online courses are invaluable.

Promotion Pathways

Clear paths to advancement within an organization not only motivate employees but also influence how they interact with their workspaces. Those aiming for managerial roles might invest more in interpersonal and leadership skills, fostering a more communal and interactive workspace atmosphere.

6. ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT

Employee alignment with organizational values and goals can profoundly impact workspace dynamics.

Workspace Pride

Committed employees often exhibit pride in their workspaces. This can manifest in well-maintained, organized and Ergonomic setups.

Peer Influence

Highly committed employees often become role models, influencing peers to adhere to best practices, whether that's in task execution or Ergonomic workspace utilization (Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J., 1991).

In sum, the psychosocial facets of IT workspaces delve deep into the intertwining of human psychology with work environments. Recognizing and addressing these dimensions ensures that, as IT continues its rapid evolution, the human aspect driven by motivation, well-being and growth remains a great support for progress.

DEPENDENT VARIABLES

1. ERGONOMIC FACTORS OF WORKSTATION IN THE IT CONTEXT

1. BODY POSTURES

In the realm of occupational health, the significance of maintaining proper body postures cannot be overstated, especially for IT Professionals who often work long hours.

Importance

Proper postures can mitigate the risk of developing musculoskeletal disorders, including carpal tunnel syndrome, lumbar strain and tension neck syndrome.

Guidelines

- The back should be straight with the lumbar region supported
- Feet should be flat on the ground
- Forearms should be parallel to the ground with elbows at an 90-degree angle
- Avoid crossing legs, which can impede circulation
- Adjustments: Utilizing standing desks or Ergonomic chairs can facilitate better postures. Workstation assessments, sometimes offered by Industries can provide personalized posture recommendations

2. DESK RELATED FACTORS

A well-designed desk serves as the foundation of an Ergonomic workspace.

Height: The desk height should allow for the user's elbows to rest comfortably at a 90-degree angle.

Depth: A deeper desk offers space to rest the arms and accommodates tools like keyboards, mouse and drawing tablets.

Layout: Integrated storage solutions, like drawers and shelves, can reduce clutter, leading to improved efficiency.

Materials: A desk with a matte finish can reduce glare, while rounded edges can prevent bruises or discomfort during prolonged work.

3. CHAIR RELATED FACTORS

A chair plays a pivotal role in supporting an individual's spine and promoting healthy postures.

Adjustability: The height should be adjustable to ensure that the feet is flat on the floor. Adjustable armrests and backrests can further customize support.

Lumbar Support: Proper lumbar support can mitigate lower back pain, a common ailment in desk jobs.

Material: Breathable fabrics can prevent sweating, while adequate cushioning offers comfort.

4. MONITOR

In the digital age, the monitor is the primary interface for IT Professionals.

Position: The top of the screen should be at or slightly below eye level to prevent neck strain.

Distance: Ideally, the monitor should be an arm's length away.

Brightness and Resolution: Adjusting these settings to ensure text and images that should be clear without straining the eyes is a crucial task. Moreover, software solutions that adjust screen warmth based on time of day can help in synchronizing with the user's circadian rhythm.

5. KEYBOARD/MOUSE

Repetitive movements with these devices can lead to strains if not managed.

Ergonomic Designs: Curved keyboards or mice designed for hand shape can reduce wrist strain.

Position: Keeping these devices at elbow height and ensuring wrists to remain neutral can prevent carpal tunnel syndrome.

Alternatives: Devices like trackballs or vertical mice can be beneficial for those with specific strains or pains.

6. WORK HABITS

Beyond physical equipment, habits play a key role in Ergonomics.

Regular Breaks: The 20-20-20 rule suggests taking a 20-second break, every 20 minutes to look at something 20 feet away, reducing eye strain.

Stretching: Simple stretches or minor exercises can refresh the body and mind.

Task Rotation: Alternating between different types of tasks can prevent cognitive fatigue.

Tidy Workspace: A decluttered workspace promotes a decluttered mind, leading to better concentration and efficiency.

ABOUT IT INDUSTRY IN INDIA

The IT Industry in India is one of the most important sectors of the economy, contributing 7.4% of the GDP in FY22. It is also a major source of employment, with over 5.4 million people employed in the sector. The IT Industry in India can be divided into two main segments

1. INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY SERVICES (IT SERVICES)

This segment provides a wide range of services to businesses, including software development, system integration and IT consulting.

2. BUSINESS PROCESS OUTSOURCING (BPO)

This segment provides back-office services to businesses, such as customer service, data entry and accounting. The IT Industry in India has grown rapidly in recent years, due to a number of factors including,

- A large pool of skilled and English-speaking workers
- A favorable government policy environment

- A growing domestic market
- A favorable investment climate

The IT Industry in India is expected to continue to grow in the coming years, driven by the growth of the global IT market and the increasing adoption of digital technologies by businesses. Some of the key trends that are shaping the IT Industry in India is Cloud Computing and Artificial Intelligence.

THE GROWTH OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

THE GROWTH OF CLOUD COMPUTING

Cloud computing is a major trend in the IT Industry, and it is expected to have a significant impact on the Indian market. Cloud computing can help businesses to reduce their IT costs and improve their agility.

THE RISE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI)

AI is another major trend that is transforming the IT Industry. AI is being used in a variety of applications such as, customer service, fraud detection and healthcare.

THE INCREASING ADOPTION OF MOBILE DEVICES

Mobile devices are becoming increasingly popular and this has a major impact on the IT Industry. Businesses need to develop mobile-friendly applications and websites in order to reach their customers.

THE GROWTH OF THE INTERNET OF THINGS (IOT)

The IOT is the network of physical objects that are connected to the internet. The IOT is expected to have a major impact on the IT Industry, as businesses use it to collect data and automate processes.

The IT Industry in India is a major driver of economic growth and job creation. It is also a major source of innovation. The IT Industry is expected to continue to grow

in the coming years and it is poised to play an even greater role in the Indian economy.

CHALLENGES THAT THE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY INDUSTRY FACES

THE SHORTAGE OF SKILLED WORKERS

The IT Industry in India is facing a shortage of skilled workers. This is due to the rapid growth of the industry and the increasing demand for skilled workers.

THE RISING COST OF TALENT

The cost of talent in the IT Industry is rising. This is due to the increasing demand for skilled workers and the limited supply of talent.

THE COMPETITION FROM OTHER COUNTRIES

The IT Industry in India is facing competition from other countries such as, China and the Philippines. These countries offer lower labor costs and a favorable investment climate.

THE NEED TO INNOVATE

The IT Industry in India needs to continue to innovate in order to stay ahead of the competition. This requires investment in research and development.

Despite these challenges, the IT Industry in India is well-positioned for continued growth. The IT Industry has a strong foundation, with a large pool of skilled workers and a favorable government policy environment. The IT Industry is also well-positioned to benefit from the growth of the global IT market and the increasing adoption of digital technologies by businesses.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to complete this research study with proven theories and determined Statistics, it is necessary to analyze the data collected in order to test the

hypothesis and answer the research questions. As already indicated in the preceding chapters, data is interpreted in a descriptive form.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

Percentage analysis method refers to the specific kind which is used in making comparison between two or more series of data collected. Percentages are based on descriptive relationship. It compares the relative items. Through the use of percentage, the data are reduced in the form with base equal to 100% which facilitate relative comparison. Percentage analysis is used to analyze the demographic variables and socio-graphic variables. Majority of the respondents have been taken for the decision-making process among all the factors taken for the study.

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

Descriptive statistics is used to analyze the acceptance of respondents towards job specialization, the acceptance of respondents towards skill requirement, the acceptance of respondents towards biological aspect, the acceptance of respondents towards workplace/ workspace design, the acceptance of respondents towards work environment based on climate, the acceptance of respondents towards work environment based on lighting, the acceptance of respondents towards work environment based on work time schedule, the acceptance of respondents towards job autonomy related to psychosocial aspect, the acceptance of respondents towards job feedback related to psychosocial aspect, the acceptance of respondents towards task variety/clarity related to psychosocial aspect, the acceptance of respondents towards mental overload/under load related to psychosocial aspect, the acceptance of respondents towards training and promotion related to

psychosocial aspect, the acceptance of respondents towards organizational commitment related to psychosocial aspect, the perception of respondents towards existing Ergonomics practices with IT companies, the opinion of respondents towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on body postures, the opinion of respondents towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on desk related factors, the opinion of respondents towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on chair related factors, the opinion of respondents towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on monitor, the opinion of respondents towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on keyboard/ mouse, the opinion of respondents towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on work habits and the suggestions of respondents towards Ergonomic factors.

While analyzing the factors, 5 point LIKER SCALING has been taken for the study where if the mean value is between 1-1.99 it shows that the respondents strongly agree towards the factors, if the mean value is between 2-2.99 it shows that the respondents agree towards the factors, if the mean value is 3 it shows that the respondents are neutral towards the factors, if the mean value is between 3.01-3.99 it shows that the respondents disagree towards the factors and if the mean value is between 4-5 it shows that the respondents strongly disagree towards the factors.

FACTOR ANALYSIS

In this research study, factor analysis is used to analyze the acceptance of respondents towards workplace / workspace design, the perception of respondents towards existing Ergonomics practices with IT Industries, the suggestions of respondents towards Ergonomic factors. While analyzing the distribution of the factors using KAISER-MEYER-OLKIN measure of

sampling adequacy, the common factors above 0.5 will be taken into consideration for decision-making process. The components having EIGENVALUES above 1.0 are taken into consideration for factor rotation. After the factors gets rotated the common factors above 0.5 are taken into consideration in the decision-making process.

KRUSKALL WALLIS TEST

With this research study, KRUSKALL WALLIS TEST is used to find the relationship between demographic variables (gender, marital status, type of family) and socio graphic variables (nature of employment) acceptance towards job specialization, acceptance towards skill requirement, acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics, acceptance towards workplace/workspace design, acceptance towards work environment based on climate, acceptance towards work environment based on lighting, acceptance towards work environment based on work time schedule, acceptance towards job autonomy related to psychosocial aspect, acceptance towards job feedback related to psychosocial aspect, acceptance towards task variety/clarity related to psychosocial aspect, acceptance towards mental overload/under load related to psychosocial aspect, acceptance towards training and promotion related to psychosocial aspect, acceptance towards organizational commitment related to psychosocial aspect, perception towards existing Ergonomics practices with IT Industries, opinion towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on body postures, opinion towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on desk related factors, opinion towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on chair related factors, opinion towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on monitor, opinion towards Ergonomic factors of

workstation based on keyboard/mouse, opinion towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on work habits and suggestions towards Ergonomic factors.

The level of significance used for the study is at 0.05 where if the significance is less than 0.05 (alternative hypothesis is accepted). This shows that the relationship exists between the compared variables and if the level of significance is greater than .05 (null hypothesis is accepted) which, shows that no relationship exists between the compared variables.

If there is any relationship between the compared variables the highest mean rank will be taken into consideration in the decision-making process.

ONE-WAY ANOVA

In this research study ONE-WAY ANOVA is used to find the difference between demographic variables (age, educational qualification, monthly salary, size of family, no. of children) and job profile (experience, no. of hours working in a week, no. of hours working in a day, no. of hours spent travelling to work) acceptance towards job specialization, acceptance towards skill requirement, acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics, acceptance towards workplace/workspace design, acceptance towards work environment based on climate, acceptance towards work environment based on lighting, acceptance towards work environment based on work time schedule, acceptance towards job autonomy related to psychosocial aspect, acceptance towards job feedback related to psychosocial aspect, acceptance towards task variety/clarity related to psychosocial aspect, acceptance towards mental overload/under load related to psychosocial aspect, acceptance towards training and promotion related to psychosocial aspect, acceptance towards

organizational commitment related to psychosocial aspect, perception towards existing Ergonomics practices with IT companies, opinion towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on body postures, opinion towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on desk related factors, opinion towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on chair related factors, opinion towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on monitor, opinion towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on keyboard/mouse, opinion towards Ergonomic factors of workstation based on work habits and suggestions towards Ergonomic factors.

The level of significance used for the study is at 0.05 where, if the significance is less than 0.05 (alternative hypothesis is accepted), it shows that no significant difference is there between the compared variables and if the level of significance is greater than .05 (null hypothesis is accepted). This shows a significant difference exists between the compared variables.

To ascertain the relationship that exists between the compared factors, 5 point LIKER SCALING method has been taken for the analysis in the study, where if the mean value is between 1-1.99 it shows that the respondents, strongly agree towards the factors, if the mean value is between 2-2.99 it shows that the respondents agree towards the factors, if the mean value is 3 it shows that the respondents are neutral towards the factors, if the mean value is between 3.01-3.99 it shows that the respondents disagree towards the factors and if the mean value is between 4-5 it shows that the respondents strongly disagree towards the factors.

SEM ANALYSIS

With this research study SEM analysis is used to find the significance of

mechanistic, biological and psychosocial factors of Ergonomics towards Ergonomic factors at workstation where the GFI and AGFI value should be between 0.8 to 0.89 and RMSEA value should be less than 0.08. If the B value is positive, it reveals that a relationship exists between the compared variables and if the B value is negative, it reveals that there is no relationship exists between the compared variables.

TO ANALYSE THE DEMOGRAPHIC AND SOCIOGRAPHIC VARIABLES OF THE EMPLOYEES WORKING IN THE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY INDUSTRY DEMOGRAPHIC AND SOCIOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

**TABLE 4.1
DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES OF THE RESPONDENTS**

Demographic Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	296	49.3
	Female	304	50.7
	Total	600	100
Age	Below 30 years	174	29
	31 - 40 years	273	45.5
	41 - 50 years	69	11.5
	Above 50 years	84	14
	Total	600	100
Educational qualification	Schoolings	51	8.5
	UG	264	44
	PG	145	24.2
	Professional degree	94	15.7
	Others	46	7.7
	Total	600	100
Monthly Salary	Up to Rs.15,000	114	19
	Rs.15,001 - Rs.30,000	192	32
	Rs.30,001 - Rs.50,000	130	21.7
	Rs.50,001 - Rs.65,000	83	13.8
	Above Rs.65,000	81	13.5
	Total	600	100

Marital Status	Married	367	61.2
	Unmarried	233	38.8
	Total	600	100
Type of family	Joint Family	310	51.7
	Nuclear Family	290	48.3
	Total	600	100
Size of family	Less than 3 members	228	38
	3 - 5 members	311	51.8
	Above 5 members	61	10.2
	Total	600	100
No. of Children	Less than 3 Children	283	47.2
	3 - 5 Children	57	9.5
	No child	260	43.3
	Total	600	100
Experience	Below 5 Years	263	43.8
	6 - 10 Years	136	22.7
	11 - 15 Years	165	27.5
	15 - 20 Years	16	2.7
	20 years and above	20	3.3
	Total	600	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table represents the results for the demographic variables of the respondents. Out of 600 respondents, 49.3% are male and 50.7% are female, 29% of the respondents have below 30 years of age, 45.5% have an age group within 31-40 years, 11.5% have an age group between 41-50 years, 14% are above 50 years of age, 8.5% of the respondents have finished their school level education, 44% have completed their UG, 24.2% have completed their PG, 15.7% finished their professional degree, 7.7% are having other educational qualification, 19% of the respondents earn a monthly salary up to Rs.15,000, 32% earn a monthly salary between Rs.15,001-Rs.30,000, 21.7% earn a monthly salary between Rs.30,001-Rs.50,000, 13.8% earn a monthly salary between Rs.50,001-Rs.65,000 and 13.5% earn a monthly salary of more than Rs.65,000.

Out of 600 respondents, 61.2% are married, 38.8% are single, 51.7% of the respondents belong to joint families, 48.3% are living in nuclear families, 38% of the respondents have less than three members in their family, 51.8% have 3-5 members in their family, 10.2% have more than five members in their family, 47.2% of the respondents have less than three children in the family, 9.5% have 3-5 children in the family, 43.3% have no child in the family, 43.8% of the respondents have less than five years of work experience, 22.7% have between 6-10 years of work experience, 27.5% have within 11-15 years of work experience, 2.7% have 15-20 years of work experience and 3.3% have 20 years and above work experience.

EXHIBIT 4.1(a)

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES OF THE RESPONDENTS

EXHIBIT 4.1(b)

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES OF THE RESPONDENTS

TABLE 4.2
SOCIO-GRAPHIC VARIABLES OF THE RESPONDENTS

Job Profile	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Nature of Employment	Permanent	270	45.0
	Temporary	330	55.0
	Total	600	100.0
How many days in a week do you normally work	Less than 5 days	160	26.7
	5 days	355	59.2
	6 days	85	14.2
	Total	600	100.0
No. of hours in a day normally working	7 - 8 hours	135	22.5
	8 - 9 hours	152	25.3
	9 - 10 hours	147	24.5
	11 - 12 hours	100	16.7
	More than 12 hours	66	11.0
	Total	600	100.0
No. of hours a day spent for traveling to work	Less than half an hour	188	31.3
	Nearly one hour	273	45.5
	Nearly two hours	75	12.5
	More than two hours	64	10.7
	Total	600	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The above table represents the results for the socio-graphic variables of the respondents. Out of 600 respondents, 45% have permanent employment, 55% have temporary employment, 26.7% of the respondents work for less than five days in a week, 59.2% work for five days in a week, 14.2% work for six days in a week, 22.5% of the respondents work for 7-8 hours in a day, 25.3% work for 8-9 hours in a day, 24.5% work for 9-10 hours in a day, 16.7% work for 11-12 hours in a day, 11% work for more than twelve hours in a day, 31.3% of the respondents spend less than half an hour in a day travelling to work, 45.5% spend nearly one hour in a day travelling to work, 12.5% spend nearly two hours in a day travelling to work and 10.7% spend more than two hours in a day travelling to work.

**EXHIBIT 4.2(a)
SOCIO-GRAPHIC VARIABLES OF THE
RESPONDENTS**

**EXHIBIT 4.2(b)
SOCIO-GRAPHIC VARIABLES OF THE
RESPONDENTS**

TO ASCERTAIN THE IMPLICATIONS OF MECHANISTIC, BIOLOGICAL AND PSYCHOSOCIAL FACTORS OF ERGONOMICS TO A THE MODULAR - STRUCTURED WORK SYSTEMS OF THE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY EMPLOYEES BASED ON MECHANISTIC, BIOLOGICAL AND PSYCHOSOCIAL FACTORS

MECHANISTIC FACTORS JOB SPECIALIZATION

**TABLE 4.3
DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR THE ACCEPTANCE OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS JOB SPECIALIZATION**

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Tasks/work patterns are simple and uncomplicated	600	1	5	2.90	1.356
Job assignment is specific to the operative	600	1	5	2.86	1.364
Tools and methods of work are specialized to the purpose of the job	600	1	5	2.77	1.320
Production volume and quality of work	600	1	5	2.96	1.309
Job holder performs multiple tasks	600	1	5	2.52	1.328
Valid N (listwise)	600				

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that the respondents agree with tasks/work patterns which are simple and uncomplicated (2.90), job assignment is specific to the operative (2.86), tools and methods of work are specialized to the purpose of the job (2.77), production volume and quality of work (2.96), job holder performs multiple tasks (2.52).

EXHIBIT 4.3

**TABLE 4.4
COMPARISON BETWEEN THE DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES (GENDER, MARITAL STATUS, TYPE OF FAMILY) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR**

ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS JOB SPECIALIZATION

Ho1: There is no relationship between the demographic variables (gender, marital status, type of family) of the respondents and their acceptance towards job specialization.

Demographic Variables	Particulars	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
Gender	Male	296	313.18	3.148	0.076
	Female	304	288.16		
	Total	600			
Marital Status	Married	367	299.32	0.044	0.834
	Unmarried	233	302.36		
	Total	600			
Type of family	Joint Family	310	306.04	0.659	0.417
	Nuclear Family	290	294.58		
	Total	600			

There is no relationship between gender (0.076), marital status (0.834) and type of family (0.417) of the respondents and their acceptance towards job specialization.

TABLE 4.5

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE JOB PROFILE (NATURE OF EMPLOYMENT) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS JOB SPECIALIZATION

Ho1a: There is no relationship between the job profile (nature of employment) of the respondents and their acceptance towards job specialization.

Job Profile	Particulars	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
Nature of Employment	Permanent	270	291.36	1.376	0.241
	Temporary	330	307.98		
	Total	600			

There is no relationship between nature of employment (0.241) of the respondents and their acceptance towards job specialization.

TABLE 4.6

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES (AGE, EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION, MONTHLY SALARY, SIZE OF FAMILY, NO. OF CHILDREN) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS JOB SPECIALIZATION

Ho1b: There is a significant difference between the demographic variables (age, educational qualification, monthly salary, size of family, no. of children) of the respondents and their acceptance towards job specialization.

Demographic Variables	Particulars	N	Mean	SD	F	Sig
Age	Below 30 years	174	2.74	0.692	3.299	0.020
	31 - 40 years	273	2.78	0.664		
	41 - 50 years	69	2.84	0.652		
	Above 50 years	84	2.54	0.761		
	Total	600	2.74	0.689		
Educational qualification	Schoolings	51	2.69	0.714	0.078	0.989
	UG	264	2.75	0.615		
	PG	145	2.74	0.691		
	Professional degree	94	2.76	0.799		
	Others	46	2.75	0.833		
Monthly Salary	Total	600	2.74	0.689	1.466	0.211
	Up to Rs.15,000	114	2.78	0.667		
	Rs.15,001 - Rs.30,000	192	2.80	0.708		
	Rs.30,001 - Rs.50,000	130	2.76	0.621		
	Rs.50,001 - Rs.65,000	83	2.68	0.727		
	Above Rs.65,000	81	2.60	0.729		
Size of family	Total	600	2.74	0.689	6.723	0.001
	Less than 3 members	228	2.81	0.652		
	3 - 5 members	311	2.75	0.681		
	Above 5 members	61	2.45	0.793		
No. of Children	Total	600	2.74	0.689	4.631	0.010
	Less than 3 Children	283	2.82	0.688		
	3 - 5 Children	57	2.54	0.658		
	No child	260	2.71	0.688		

There is a significant difference between educational qualification (0.989), monthly salary (0.211) of the respondents and their acceptance towards job specialization. There is no significant difference between age (0.020), size of family (0.001), no. of children (0.010) of the respondents and their acceptance towards job specialization.

Age

The employees below 30 years of age (2.74), from age group between 31-40 years (2.78), between 41-50 years (2.84) and more than 50 years of age (2.54) agree towards job specialization.

Size of Family

The employees with less than 3 members (2.81), between 3 – 5 members (2.75) and more than 5 members in their family (2.45) agree towards job specialization.

No. of Children

The employees with less than 3 children (2.82), between 3-5 children (2.54) and the employees who have no child (2.71) agree towards job specialization.

TABLE 4.7

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE JOB PROFILE (EXPERIENCE, NO OF HOURS WORKING IN A WEEK, NO. OF HOURS WORKING IN A DAY, NO. OF HOURS SPENT TRAVELLING TO WORK) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS JOB SPECIALIZATION

Ho1c: There is a significant difference between the job profile (experience, no. of hours working in a week, no. of hours working in a day, no. of hours spent travelling to work) of the respondents and their acceptance towards job specialization.

Job Profile	Particulars	N	Mean	Sd	F	Sig
Experience	Below 5 Years	263	2.80	0.695	2.560	0.038
	6 - 10 Years	136	2.61	0.669		
	11 - 15 Years	165	2.80	0.670		
	15 - 20 Years	16	2.65	0.465		
	20 years and above	20	2.52	0.905		
	Total	600	2.74	0.689		
No. of hours working in a week	Less than 5 days	160	2.69	0.634	6.420	0.002
	5 days	355	2.82	0.657		
	6 days	85	2.54	0.856		
	Total	600	2.74	0.689		
No. of hours working in a day	7 - 8 hours	135	2.65	0.710	1.435	0.221
	8 - 9 hours	152	2.75	0.639		
	9 - 10 hours	147	2.72	0.708		
	11 - 12 hours	100	2.84	0.632		
	More than 12 hours	66	2.84	0.783		
	Total	600	2.74	0.689		
No. of hours spent travelling to work	Less than half an hour	188	2.72	0.667	2.134	0.095
	Nearly one hour	273	2.74	0.685		
	Nearly two hours	75	2.66	0.734		
	More than two hours	64	2.94	0.699		
	Total	600	2.74	0.689		

There is a significant difference between no. of hours working in a day (0.221) and no. of hours spent travelling to work (0.095) of the respondents and their acceptance towards job specialization. There is no significant difference between experience (0.038) and no. of hours working in a week (0.002) of the respondents and their acceptance towards job specialization.

Experience

Employees with less than 5 years of work experience (2.80), between 6-10 years (2.61) 11-15 years (2.80), 15-20 years (2.65) and more than 20 years of

work experience (2.52) agree towards job specialization.

SKILL REQUIREMENT

TABLE 4.8

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR THE ACCEPTANCE OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS SKILL REQUIREMENT

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Job requires knowledge and skillful ability	600	1	5	2.11	1.169
Job demands training for skill acquisition	600	1	5	2.28	1.184
Worker makes frequent mistakes at work	600	1	5	2.54	1.229
Job demands frequent rotation, as directed	600	1	5	2.44	1.076
Work operation is machine paced/assisted by automation	600	1	5	2.17	1.132
Valid N (listwise)	600				

Source: Primary Data

No. of Hours Working in a Week

The employees working for less than 5 days in a week (2.69), working for 5 days in a week (2.82) and working for 6 days in a week (2.54) agree towards job specialization.

The above table shows that the respondents agree with job requiring knowledge and skillful ability (2.11), job demanding training for skill acquisition (2.28), worker makes frequent mistakes at work (2.54), job demanding frequent rotation as directed (2.44) and work operation is machine paced/assisted by automation (2.17).

EXHIBIT 4.4

TABLE 4.9

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES (GENDER, MARITAL STATUS, TYPE OF FAMILY) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS SKILL REQUIREMENT

Ho2: There is no relationship between the demographic variables (gender, marital status, type of family) of the respondents and their acceptance towards skill requirement.

Demographic Variables	Particulars	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
Gender	Male	296	306.41	0.687	0.407
	Female	304	294.74		
	Total	600			
Marital Status	Married	367	330.50	28.619	0.000
	Unmarried	233	253.24		
	Total	600			
Type of family	Joint Family	310	309.35	1.689	0.194
	Nuclear Family	290	291.04		
	Total	600			

There is no relationship between gender (0.407) and type of family (0.194) of the respondents and their acceptance towards skill requirement. There is a relationship between marital status (0.000) of the respondents and their acceptance towards skill requirement.

Marital Status

Married respondents (330.50) have a higher level of acceptance towards skill requirement.

TABLE 4.10

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE JOB PROFILE (NATURE OF EMPLOYMENT) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS SKILL REQUIREMENT

Ho2a: There is no relationship between the job profile (nature of employment) of the respondents and their acceptance towards skill requirement.

Job Profile	Particulars	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
Nature of Employment	Permanent	270	301.29	0.010	0.919
	Temporary	330	299.85		
	Total	600			

There is no relationship between nature of employment (0.919) of the respondents and their acceptance towards skill requirement.

TABLE 4.11

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES (AGE, EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION, MONTHLY SALARY, SIZE OF FAMILY, NO. OF CHILDREN) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS SKILL REQUIREMENT

Ho2b: There is a significant difference between the demographic variables (age, educational qualification, monthly salary, size of family, no. of children) of the respondents and their acceptance towards skill requirement.

Demographic Variables	Particulars	N	Mean	SD	F	Sig
Age	Below 30 years	174	2.27	0.571	0.991	0.396
	31 - 40 years	273	2.35	0.624		
	41 - 50 years	69	2.25	0.536		
	Above 50 years	84	2.35	0.709		
	Total	600	2.32	0.612		
Educational qualification	Schoolings	51	2.36	0.660	5.701	0.000
	UG	264	2.19	0.571		
	PG	145	2.39	0.593		
	Professional degree	94	2.44	0.652		
	Others	46	2.51	0.643		
	Total	600	2.32	0.612		
Monthly Salary	Up to Rs.15,000	114	2.22	0.541	1.780	0.131
	Rs.15,001 - Rs.30,000	192	2.38	0.642		
	Rs.30,001 - Rs.50,000	130	2.38	0.614		
	Rs.50,001 - Rs.65,000	83	2.27	0.606		
	Above Rs.65,000	81	2.26	0.625		
	Total	600	2.32	0.612		
Size of family	Less than 3 members	228	2.26	0.607	1.842	0.159
	3 - 5 members	311	2.34	0.608		
	Above 5 members	61	2.40	0.645		
	Total	600	2.32	0.612		
No. of Children	Less than 3 Children	283	2.45	0.653	14.481	0.000
	3 - 5 Children	57	2.26	0.604		
	No child	260	2.18	0.533		
	Total	600	2.32	0.612		

There is a significant difference between age (0.396), monthly salary (0.131), size of family (0.159) of the respondents and their acceptance towards skill requirement. There is no significant difference between educational qualification (0.000), no. of children (0.000) of the respondents and their acceptance towards skill requirement.

Educational Qualification

The employees who have completed their school education (2.36), UG (2.19), PG (2.39), professional degree (2.44) and from other educational background (2.51) agree towards skill requirement of the company.

No. of Children

Employees with less than 3 children (2.45), between 3-5 children (2.26) and the employees with no child in their family (2.18) agree towards skill requirement of the company.

TABLE 4.12

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE JOB PROFILE (EXPERIENCE, NO. OF HOURS WORKING IN A WEEK, NO. OF HOURS WORKING IN A DAY, NO. OF HOURS SPENT TRAVELLING TO WORK) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS SKILL REQUIREMENT

Ho2c: There is a significant difference between the job profile (experience, no. of hours working in a week, no. of hours working in a day, no. of hours spent travelling to work) of the respondents and their acceptance towards skill requirement.

Job Profile	Particulars	N	Mean	SD	F	Sig
Experience	Below 5 Years	263	2.32	0.583	0.988	0.414
	6 - 10 Years	136	2.27	0.560		
	11 - 15 Years	165	2.32	0.644		
	15 - 20 Years	16	2.54	0.424		
	20 years and above	20	2.46	1.047		
	Total	600	2.32	0.612		
No. of hours working in a week	Less than 5 days	160	2.18	0.530	12.846	0.000
	5 days	355	2.32	0.604		
	6 days	85	2.58	0.704		
	Total	600	2.32	0.612		

Job Profile	Particulars	N	Mean	SD	F	Sig
No. of hours working in a day	7 - 8 hours	135	2.20	0.518	3.937	0.004
	8 - 9 hours	152	2.23	0.556		
	9 - 10 hours	147	2.38	0.584		
	11 - 12 hours	100	2.46	0.660		
	More than 12 hours	66	2.41	0.814		
	Total	600	2.32	0.612		
No. of hours spent travelling to work	Less than half an hour	188	2.24	0.618	18.147	0.000
	Nearly one hour	273	2.21	0.559		
	Nearly two hours	75	2.51	0.621		
	More than two hours	64	2.75	0.573		
	Total	600	2.32	0.612		

There is no significant difference between no. of hours working in a week (0.000), no. of hours working in a day (0.004) and no. of hours spent travelling to work (0.000) of the respondents and their acceptance towards skill requirement. There is a significant difference between experience (0.414) of the respondents and their acceptance towards skill requirement.

No. of Hours Working in a Week

The employees working for less than 5 days (2.69), working for 5 days (2.82) and working for 6 days in a week (2.54) agree towards skill requirement.

No. of Hours Working in a Day

The employees working for 7-8 hours (2.20), 8-9 hours (2.23) 9-10 hours (2.38), 11-12 hours (2.46) and more than 12 hours in a day (2.41) agree towards skill requirement.

No. of Hours Spent Travelling to Work

Employees travelling less than half an hour to reach the office (2.24), nearly one hour (2.21), nearly two hours (2.51)

and more than two hours to reach the office (2.75) agree towards skill requirement.

BIOLOGICAL ASPECT

TABLE 4.13

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR THE ACCEPTANCE OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS BIOLOGICAL ASPECT

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Physical activity is entirely determined and regulated by the worker	600	1	5	2.50	1.167
Worker maintains target-oriented pace	600	1	5	2.58	1.299
Job implies frequently repeated movements	600	1	5	2.58	1.209
Cardio respiratory demand of the job	600	1	5	2.65	1.329
Job demands high muscular strength exertion	600	1	5	2.61	1.331
Job (operation of handle, steering wheel, pedal brake) is predominantly static work	600	1	5	2.69	1.271
Job requires fixed working position (sitting or standing)	600	1	5	2.70	1.274
Valid N (listwise)	600				

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that the respondents agree with biological aspects like physical activity is entirely determined and regulated by the worker (2.50), worker maintain a target-oriented pace and job implies frequently repeated movements (2.58), cardio respiratory demand of the job (2.65), job demands high muscular strength exertion (2.61), job (operation of handle, steering wheel, pedal brake) is predominantly static work (2.69) and job

requires fixed working position (sitting or standing) (2.70).

EXHIBIT 4.5

TABLE 4.14

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES (GENDER, MARITAL STATUS, TYPE OF FAMILY) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS BIOLOGICAL ASPECT RELATED TO ERGONOMICS

Ho3: There is no relationship between the demographic variables (gender, marital status, type of family) of the respondents and their acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

Demographic Variables	Particulars	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
Gender	Male	296	305.23	0.439	0.508
	Female	304	295.89		
	Total	600			
Marital Status	Married	367	287.57	5.294	0.021
	Unmarried	233	320.87		
	Total	600			
Type of family	Joint Family	310	284.70	5.361	0.021
	Nuclear Family	290	317.38		
	Total	600			

There is no relationship between gender (0.508) of the respondents and their acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics. There is a relationship between marital status and type of family (0.021) of the respondents and their acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

Marital Status

Unmarried respondents (320.87) have a higher level of acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

Type of Family

Respondents living in nuclear families (317.38) have a higher level of acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

TABLE 4.15

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE JOB PROFILE (NATURE OF EMPLOYMENT) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS BIOLOGICAL ASPECT RELATED TO ERGONOMICS

Ho3a: There is no relationship between the job profile (nature of employment) of the respondents and their acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

TABLE 4.15

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE JOB PROFILE (NATURE OF EMPLOYMENT) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS BIOLOGICAL ASPECT RELATED TO ERGONOMICS

Ho3a: There is no relationship between the job profile (nature of employment) of the respondents and their acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

Job Profile	Particulars	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
Nature of Employment	Permanent	270	298.11	0.094	0.759
	Temporary	330	302.46		
	Total	600			

There is no relationship between nature of employment (0.795) of the respondents and their acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

TABLE 4.16

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES (AGE, EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION, MONTHLY SALARY, SIZE OF FAMILY,

NO. OF CHILDREN) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS BIOLOGICAL ASPECT RELATED TO ERGONOMICS

Ho3b: There is a significant difference between the demographic variables (age, educational qualification, monthly salary, size of family, no. of children) of the respondents and their acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

Demographic Variables	Particulars	N	Mean	Sd	F	Sig
Age	Below 30 years	174	2.62	0.544	0.755	0.520
	31 - 40 years	273	2.58	0.552		
	41 - 50 years	69	2.65	0.568		
	Above 50 years	84	2.68	0.611		
	Total	600	2.62	0.560		
Educational qualification	Schoolings	51	2.72	0.682	2.696	0.030
	UG	264	2.68	0.533		
	PG	145	2.54	0.538		
	Professional degree	94	2.54	0.593		
	Others	46	2.53	0.522		
	Total	600	2.62	0.560		
Monthly Salary	Up to Rs.15,000	114	2.62	0.584	0.506	0.731
	Rs.15,001 - Rs.30,000	192	2.65	0.561		
	Rs.30,001 - Rs.50,000	130	2.56	0.503		
	Rs.50,001 - Rs.65,000	83	2.63	0.590		
	Above Rs.65,000	81	2.60	0.585		
	Total	600	2.62	0.560		
Size of family	Less than 3 members	228	2.64	0.516	0.841	0.432
	3 - 5 members	311	2.62	0.583		
	Above 5 members	61	2.53	0.601		
	Total	600	2.62	0.560		
No. of Children	Less than 3 Children	283	2.58	0.573	1.714	0.181
	3 - 5 Children	57	2.60	0.468		
	No child	260	2.66	0.563		
	Total	600	2.62	0.560		

There is a significant difference between age (0.520), monthly salary (0.731), size of family (0.432) and no. of children (0.181) of the respondents and their acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics. There is no significant difference between educational qualification (0.030) of the respondents and their acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

Educational Qualification

Respondents who completed their school education (2.72), UG (2.68), PG (2.54), professional degree (2.54) and from other educational background (2.53) agree towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

TABLE 4.17

COMPARISON BETWEEN THE JOB PROFILE (EXPERIENCE, NO. OF HOURS WORKING IN A WEEK, NO. OF HOURS WORKING IN A DAY, NO. OF HOURS SPENT TRAVELLING TO WORK) OF THE RESPONDENTS AND THEIR ACCEPTANCE TOWARDS BIOLOGICAL ASPECT RELATED TO ERGONOMICS

Ho3c: There is a significant difference between the job profile (experience, no. of hours working in a week, no. of hours working in a day, no. of hours spent travelling to work) of the respondents and their acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

Job Profile	Particulars	N	Mean	Sd	F	Sig
Experience	Below 5 Years	263	2.62	0.530	0.415	0.798
	6 - 10 Years	136	2.63	0.559		
	11 - 15 Years	165	2.58	0.556		
	15 - 20 Years	16	2.64	0.416		
	20 years and above	20	2.74	0.983		
	Total	600	2.62	0.560		

Job Profile	Particulars	N	Mean	Sd	F	Sig
No. of hours working in a week	Less than 5 days	160	2.60	0.572	0.176	0.839
	5 days	355	2.63	0.528		
	6 days	85	2.60	0.664		
	Total	600	2.62	0.560		
No. of hours working in a day	7 - 8 hours	135	2.52	0.548	1.604	0.172
	8 - 9 hours	152	2.63	0.574		
	9 - 10 hours	147	2.62	0.575		
	11 - 12 hours	100	2.71	0.507		
	More than 12 hours	66	2.63	0.583		
	Total	600	2.62	0.560		
No. of hours spent travelling to work	Less than half an hour	188	2.60	0.549	1.395	0.243
	Nearly one hour	273	2.65	0.528		
	Nearly two hours	75	2.64	0.626		
	More than two hours	64	2.50	0.634		
	Total	600	2.62	0.560		

There is a significant difference between the experience (0.798), no. of hours working in a week (0.839), no. of hours working in a day (0.172), no. of hours spent travelling to work (0.243) of the respondents and their acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

WORKPLACE/WORKSPACE DESIGN

FACTOR ANALYSIS

The factor analysis has been used to analyze the modular-structured work systems of the IT employees based on workplace/workspace design. This statistical approach is a way of condensing the information contained in a number of original variables into a smaller set of dimensions (factors) with a minimum loss in respect to the information collected. Before applying the Factor Analysis, the data adequacy test for factor analysis was checked using KMO and Bartlett's Test. In this present study, the Principal Component analysis is used as the extraction method on the correlation matrix of 13 statements and the result was rotated

using Kaiser’s Varimax criteria. First and foremost, the Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) measure for sample adequacy and Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity were assessed.

TABLE 4.18

KMO AND BARTLETT’S TEST FOR THE ACCEPTANCE OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS WORKPLACE/WORKSPACE DESIGN

TABLE 4.18

KMO AND BARTLETT’S TEST FOR THE ACCEPTANCE OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS WORKPLACE/WORKSPACE DESIGN

KMO and BARTLETT’S Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.563
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	325.874
	df	78
	Sig.	.000

The above table reveals that the score for KMO test is high at 0.563, indicating ‘Good’ reliability among the items in the scale. Therefore, all 13 items in the scale which were used to analyse the Modular-Structured Work systems of the IT employees who are based on workplace/workspace design. As the data is highly reliable and internally consistent, it was further subjected to principal component method of factor analysis with ‘VARIMAX ROTATION’. The result of the factor analysis is presented, and the following table shows EIGEN VALUE of ‘VARIMAX ROTATION’ for all the statements.

TABLE 4.19

TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED FOR THE ACCEPTANCE OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS WORKPLACE/WORKSPACE DESIGN

Component	TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED								
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.614	12.419	12.419	1.614	12.419	12.419	1.517	11.671	11.671
2	1.498	11.526	23.945	1.498	11.526	23.945	1.376	10.586	22.257
3	1.299	9.994	33.939	1.299	9.994	33.939	1.354	10.419	32.676
4	1.169	8.992	42.931	1.169	8.992	42.931	1.185	9.118	41.794
5	1.021	7.853	50.783	1.021	7.853	50.783	1.169	8.990	50.783
6	.972	7.477	58.261						
7	.949	7.303	65.564						
8	.845	6.496	72.060						
9	.804	6.186	78.247						
10	.788	6.058	84.305						
11	.739	5.683	89.988						
12	.685	5.272	95.260						
13	.616	4.740	100.000						
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.									

Out of 13 components, eigenvalues of more than 1 are taken for factor rotation. In this study 5 components were taken and the first component contributes 12.41%, the second component contributes 11.52%, the third component contributes 9.99%, the fourth component contributes 8.99% and fifth component contributes 7.85%.

EXHIBIT 4.6

SCREE PLOT FOR THE ACCEPTANCE OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS WORKPLACE/ WORKSPACE DESIGN

TABLE 4.20
ROTATED COMPONENT MATRIX FOR THE ACCEPTANCE OF RESPONDENTS TOWARDS WORKPLACE/WORKSPACE DESIGN

ROTATED COMPONENT MATRIX ^A					
	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
Workplace is compatible with human dimensions	-.116	-.105	.374	.133	.361
Work distance is away from normal reach in the horizontal or vertical plane	-.113	.757	.042	.076	.313
Height of work desk/equipment is fixed or minimally adjustable	-.022	.758	.056	-.140	-.162
No space for subsidiary operations (e.g., inspection and maintenance)	.021	.086	-.081	-.115	.807
Workstations have obstacles, protruding parts or sharp edges	-.162	.063	.658	-.055	-.238
Seat dimensions (e.g., seat height, back rest) mismatch with human dimensions	.100	.083	.528	-.008	.183
Minimum adjustability of seat	.644	.043	-.014	.088	.076
Work seat provides no hold/support	-.014	-.263	.107	.718	.155
Absence of vibration damping mechanism in the work seat	-.050	-.066	.479	.424	-.157
Non-availability of storage space for tools, personal articles	.573	.024	-.224	-.132	-.185
Doorways, entrance/exit routes, or corridors are restricted	.529	.005	.424	-.172	-.078
Handholds and footholds demand awkward position of limbs	.649	-.177	.008	.097	.061
Supports are unrecognizable by their place, form or construction	.083	.302	-.141	.606	-.272
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.					

Rotation Method: Quartimax with Kaiser Normalization.		
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.		

The above table shows the factor loadings are produced by the factor analysis. It is understood that each statement corresponding to the highlighted factor loading is correlated with the factor corresponding to that factor loading. It is understood that EIGEN VALUE is more than one for first five factors. Higher the factor loading, stronger is the correlation between the factors and the statements. In the rotated component matrix, only those common variables that had a factor loading which is greater than 0.5 for all 13 statements were grouped under their respective derived factors for further analysis.

FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS, CONCLUSION, FUTURE SCOPE OF THE STUDY

FINDINGS

DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES OF THE RESPONDENTS

Most of the respondents are female and are in an age group between 31 - 40 years.

Majority of the respondents have finished their under graduate degree and earn monthly salary within Rs.15,001 - Rs.30,000.

Maximum of the respondents are married and belong to joint families.

Most of the respondents have 3 - 5 members and less than three children in their family.

Majority of the respondents have less than five years of work experience.

SOCIO-GRAPHIC VARIABLES OF THE RESPONDENTS

Most of the respondents have temporary jobs.

Majority of the respondents work for five days in a week.

Most of the respondents work for 8 - 9 hours in a day.

Most of the respondents spend nearly one hour travelling to work.

MECHANISTIC FACTORS

JOB SPECIALIZATION

The respondents agree with tasks/work patterns which are simple and uncomplicated, job assignment is specific to the operative, tools and methods of work are specialized to the purpose of the job, production volume and quality of work (2.96), job holder performs multiple tasks.

The employees below 30 years of age, from age group between 31 - 40 years, between 41 - 50 years and more than 50 years of age agree towards job specialization.

The employees with less than 3 members, between 3 - 5 members and more than 5 members in their family agree towards job specialization.

The employees with less than 3 children, between 3 - 5 children and the employees who have no child agree towards job specialization.

Employees with less than 5 years of work experience, between 6 - 10 years, 11 - 15 years, 15 - 20 years and more than

20 years of work experience agree towards job specialization.

The employees working for less than 5 days, 5 days and 6 days in a week (2.54) agree towards job specialization.

SKILL REQUIREMENT

The respondents agree with job requiring knowledge and skillful ability, job demanding training for skill acquisition, prevention of mistakes at work, job demanding frequent rotation as directed and work operation is machine paced/assisted by automation and are determined to agree to have a higher level of acceptance towards skill requirement.

Married respondents have a higher level of acceptance towards skill requirement.

The employees who have completed their school education, UG, PG, professional degree and from other educational background agree towards skill requirement of the company.

Employees with less than 3 children, between 3 - 5 children and the employees with no child in their family agree towards skill requirement of the company.

The employees working for less than 5 days, 5 days and 6 days in a week agree towards skill requirement.

The employees working for 7 - 8 hours, 8 - 9 hours, 9 - 10 hours, 11 - 12 hours and more than 12 hours in a day agree towards skill requirement.

Employees travelling less than half an hour to reach the office, nearly one hour, nearly two hours and more than two hours to reach the office agree towards skill requirement.

BIOLOGICAL ASPECT

The respondents who agree with biological aspects are those whose physical activity is entirely determined and regulated by the worker. The worker

maintains a target - oriented pace and job implies frequently repeated movements, cardio respiratory demand of the job, job demands high muscular strength exertion, job (operation of handle, steering wheel, pedal brake) is a predominantly static work and job requires fixed working position (sitting or standing).

Unmarried respondents living in nuclear families have a higher level of acceptance towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

Respondents who completed their school education, UG, PG, Professional degree and from other educational background agree towards biological aspect related to Ergonomics.

WORKPLACE/WORKSPACE DESIGN

The respondents agree with work distance is away from normal reach in the horizontal or vertical plane and work seat provides no hold/support. The respondents disagree with the height of work desk/equipment is fixed or minimally adjustable.

Male respondents have a higher level of acceptance towards workplace/ workspace design.

The employees earning a monthly salary up to Rs.15,000 between Rs.15,001 - Rs.30,000, Rs.30,001 - Rs.50,000, Rs.50,001 - Rs.65,000 and above Rs.65,000 agree towards workplace /workspace design of the company.

The employees with less than 3 members, between 3-5 members and more than 5 members in their family agree towards workplace/workspace design of the company.

The employees spending less than half an hour a day, nearly one hour a day, nearly 2 hours a day and more than 2 hours a day travelling to work agree towards workplace/workspace design of the company.

TO BRIEF OUT THE STUDY

Ergonomics in the IT workspace represents a vital intersection of health, efficiency and design. As delineated in our discussion, every aspect, from the intricacies of desk layout to the nuances of work habits, bears significance in shaping the holistic well-being and productivity of IT Professionals. The meticulous attention to these facets underscores the essence of proactive health measures and optimized performance in our digital era. By harmonizing the physical with the psychological aspects and integrating these within the digital workspace, Ergonomics elevates the work environment from mere functionality to one of enhanced well-being. As the IT sector continues to evolve at a rapid pace, anchored by innovation and relentless demand, such Ergonomic considerations becomes not just recommendations but also an essential imperative. They ensure that while one surge ahead in the digital frontier, it makes a mark to remain anchored in the foundational principles of health, comfort and sustainable productivity.

CONCLUSION

In summary, while a foundational understanding of Ergonomics in IT settings exists, a more integrated, region-specific and application-oriented exploration of how mechanistic, biological and psychosocial factors intersect at the workstation remains a notable gap. Addressing this will not only enrich the academic discourse but also have tangible benefits for IT Professionals in Coimbatore and potentially in other similar burgeoning IT hubs. Based on the considerations no study intended to analyze the significance of mechanistic, biological and psychosocial factors of Ergonomics towards Ergonomic factors at workstation and the same has been take as main gap towards the study.

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